

Abstract. The article considers the issue of attaining prospective management of each enterprise in the development of business structures as a component of the management of our country's development strategy. In this instance, the need to define a strategy and act accordingly was interpreted as a trend in the formation of private business structures associated with the growth of market relations in the country.

Key words: management, market economy, entrepreneurship, necessity, strategic management, planning, risk.

INTRODUCTION: It is well known that in order to expedite the reforms being implemented in our country, it is crucial to cultivate entrepreneurship comprehensively in the economy. One of the tasks related to the development of entrepreneurship outlined in the "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan" is "integration of small businesses into the international community, increase and diversification of export potential, reform of the marketing system, improvement of innovative and strategic management, export of products to foreign markets, and active promotion of national brands abroad." The value of "push" is 1.151. "Rapid development of the activities of entrepreneurs is the most important guarantee of the development of our society and our prosperous way of life, as well as the most important guarantee of the stable growth of our economy" [2.68]. The new stage of entrepreneurship in our country is a new, civilized stage of entrepreneurial activity in the independent Republic of Uzbekistan, which is characterized by a process of enthusiasm, following the lead of the world's most developed nations. The development of the business climate in Uzbekistan is a distinct indication of this. In order to achieve the desired economic growth, it would be prudent for an entrepreneur operating in our country today to acquire a comprehensive understanding of the substance of strategic management of businesses. It aids the modern entrepreneur in acquiring the theoretical and practical skills that are fundamental not only to his own but also to social development. Literature review on the topic. In our scientific research, we theorized on the basis of the historical decisions of our nation's leader aiming at the comprehensive development of entrepreneurship, delineating the country's development strategy, and putting market economy principles into practice [1–4].

We organized the scientific perspectives on the subject as follows: In the works of foreign scholars R.S. Kaplan and D.P. Norton, the primary emphasis is placed on assessing the enterprise's and organization's strategic management systems' effectiveness [5]. [6] According to I. Ansoff, the appraisal of the enterprise's prospects and the factors influencing them are examined within the strategic management system. In M. Porter's opinion, the role and process of innovation in the development of companies and the issues surrounding the attainment of competitive advantage are investigated [7]. G.Sh.Khonkeldieva highlighted solutions to management issues by evaluating organizational-economic indicators and increasing the economic efficiency of businesses [8]. R.R. Abduraupov investigated the improvement of the economic activity management mechanisms of foreign-invested enterprises in our country [9].

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In contrast to the aforementioned scientific views, B.V. Nasimov, in the context of contemporary globalization and democratic market reforms, systematically emphasizes the evaluation of the factors affecting the improvement of the enterprise's efficiency and the development of its economic activity in the strategic management system [10]; Nodirkhanov J.N., Theoretical foundations of strategic management of small businesses and entrepreneurial enterprises. We did not, however, discover in the scientific literature the opinion that the strategic management of each business enterprise is a requirement and a component of the management of our country's development strategy.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

In this article, we examined the administration of business enterprises from a historical, economic, logical, deterministic, and discourse analysis perspective. In addition, scientific abstraction and systematic analysis were employed in the conduct of research.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Historically, we are all aware that any labor activity, whether large or small, whether in the manufacturing or service sector, requires varying degrees of management. In other words, the process of continuous creation of material commodities requires some level of management in order to guarantee the development of human society. Consequently, even in small organizations, labor activities performed by two or more individuals are governed by management. Nonetheless, in order to control an object, the controller must be aware of its properties. According to the national encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, management (in economics) is the process of regulating and directing the state of the economic system of an economic object; it also refers to the conscious, purposeful influence of subjects, agencies, and economic objects in order to direct their activities and achieve the desired outcomes [13]. During the course of his activities, an entrepreneur must manage a team, a brigade, a workshop, or a department, as well as the enterprise as a whole.

Therefore, the entrepreneur-leader must understand the industry's particulars in order to manage the labor force. These include: the structure of production and technological processes; the material and moral aspects of the use of human resources; the continuity and efficiency of the use of financial resources; knowledge of how to constantly ensure the management structure and its optimality; specific necessary and organizational aspects of business activity and anticipated risks; constant consideration of the fiscal policy of the country in which business is conducted, etc. Profit is therefore the objective of an entrepreneur when establishing a business. This is due to this businessman's wisdom or philosophical views. Thus, every entrepreneur who establishes a new business endeavors to generate a profit, although not everyone knows how. However, an enterprising individual or group endowed with a novel concept differs from others in that they have a comprehensive understanding of profitable avenues. Through extensive research, they are able to determine with greater precision which sector, industry, activity, or geographical region tends to attract investment today. Nonetheless, any ambitious entrepreneur aspires not only to attain the average profit rate in market competition but also to earn more profit. Consequently, such motivation encourages the entrepreneur to attain superiority in any competition. It surely does not occur naturally. This ambition, the intended objective, necessitates knowledge, experience, and high-level skills from the entrepreneur, and this circumstance creates the entrepreneur's inner experiences, plans, and

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objectives with the necessary precision. This information ultimately influences the entrepreneur's future plans.

In other words, the entrepreneur is opposed to the need for prospective planning in the enterprise's activities and, consequently, the obligation to create it. In this manner, the entrepreneur has a flawless long-term plan for the expansion of his business. Now that it is necessary to implement this long-term, profitable plan, the question of how to do so naturally arises. We believe that such a circumstance necessitates strategic management of the enterprise and the pursuit of a transparent mechanism for its operation. This circumstance, however, necessitates strategic management based on the requirements of economic laws governing market relations. So, what is a "strategy" exactly? As is common knowledge, the issues surrounding the use of this term in circulation are discussed in ER 480 and 221. In the history of ancient China, it was conveyed in the commander Sun Tzu's book "The Art of Strategy." The term "strategy" is derived from the Greek word "strategos," which means "leadership" or "the art of the general." It still refers to the military commander's ability to organize military operations. Nonetheless, "priority" enabled Alexander the Great to conquer the world. Consequently, the strategy has earned him a global reputation.

Consequently, if we focus on the original meaning, "Priority" is a profound, comprehensively developed complex, a plan, which is the accomplishment of the enterprise's primary task and the attainment of its objectives. It is important to note that we do not believe it is necessary to recall the various scientific approaches to defining Strategic Management [see p. 11.80] at this time.

Hence, the strategy is a planning policy in the most fundamental sense (on the path to the intended objective). From the perspective of an enterprise operating in a market economy as well as the military, strategy refers to the direction of action and the discipline of guiding toward the achievement of an objective. Therefore, strategy is the time to direct the goal's implementation. In other words, when making a decision for each process situation, it is necessary to identify the most significant issues and orientations in the development of particular actions, as well as the optimal mechanism for their implementation.

Strategic management is the management of a business firm in such a way that it relies on human potential, focuses production activities on consumer demand, makes rapid adaptations and timely changes in the organization, and, over the long term, maintains its goals and achieves the desired outcome. In other terms, strategic management-the strategic management of small businesses and business entities-is a set of actions that represent the measures intended to achieve the enterprise's or organization's long-term objective.

These factors pertain to the scope of microeconomics (enterprise) in a market-based economy. So, let's assume that the majority of businesses in our nation have implemented strategic management and are pursuing their objectives. What will occur if this strategic management process is implemented on a national scale? Apparently, the answer to this question is straightforward. If every target firm (enterprise) in the country grasps the essence of the strategic management that we have outlined and realizes its potential, then we will attain a strategic management system on a national scale. The administration of the country's economy will be vested with strategic authority, and we will ultimately reach the level of development that has been intended for many years. Logically, it follows that as each individual business firm is able to provide strategic management according to its own interests, it will become

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increasingly compatible with the interests of society as a whole. In his time, Adam Smith, the famous English classical economist, observed such laws of development. Even today, it is essential to master the law of interest compatibility.

Thus, Adam Smith demonstrated the relationship between entrepreneurs and society during his time. At first inspection, it appears that their interests do not always align with those of society as a whole. "Each individual endeavors to maximize the value of the goods he produces by maximizing the use of his capital. Typically, he does not put the welfare of society first, and he is unaware of the extent to which he enables it. He only considers his own interests and works only for the sake of the name he sees, and at the same time, with the assistance of an invisible "hand," he enters a path leading to an objective that has nothing to do with his own interests. "An entrepreneur who acts solely for his own interests serves society's interests more effectively than when he intends to do so deliberately" [14. 392].

As a result, "they are completely occupied with various plans and projects throughout their entire lives, and they are distinguished by the fact that they understand more things and think better than the landed gentry" [14.391]. Such plans and It is evident that the most vital aspects of labor are managed, regulated, and monitored in order to generate a profit from the innovations introduced by the projects. "Experienced individuals acknowledge that a great deal depends on management. Business administration is a multidimensional, uncharted, and borderless science. And commerce is not merely a means to wealth. Perhaps serving society entails meeting people's requirements. In commerce, interests converge. The purpose of business is to satisfy the diverse requirements of people and to make life attractive and full" [12.4]. This indicates that the interests of entrepreneurs and the entire society are aligned.

Subsequently, a closer examination reveals that the primary interest (motive) that indirectly motivates entrepreneurship is greater than profit. Yes, this effort is a covert operation. In other words, the entrepreneur's personal economic interests are always the same as those of the socially recognized subject—employees, entrepreneurs, etc. They are inextricably linked and aligned with social and collective interests at all times. In conclusion, the strategic management of businesses is the primary component of the strategic management structure of our country.

Therefore, the rational, effective strategic management of firms, companies, or individual territories is directly related to and influences the strategic management of our nation. Thus, it is dialectic. Additionally, we should keep in mind that "When it comes to economic growth, the best strategy is to increase domestic demand" [17.94]. Although domestic demand initially increases, this ultimately increases the country's export potential. We believe this demonstrates the success of reasonable strategic management. So, what is the most effective management strategy here? Initially, each firm, enterprise, or organization must establish a long-term, optimal-priority alternative management mechanism based on all of its capabilities. Therefore, precise adherence to the principles of strategic management is necessary.

DISCUSSION

On the basis of the preceding, it can be concluded that the management philosophy of every enterprise operating under the current conditions of market competition must be formulated, i.e., an ambitious entrepreneur must recognize the importance of strategic management. This implies that an entrepreneur must have an accurate understanding of the

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existence of his business. To comprehend the economic development laws, it is necessary to expand one's knowledge based on ongoing information. "Successful managers are as rare as pearls in the sand».

According to the conclusion of business leaders with decades of experience in this field, strategic management in corporations should examine the following topics: - Creation of strategic management thinking in the management of enterprise activities; - formation, management, and organization of a strategic process by an entrepreneur in his enterprise; - analysis of external and internal environment (SWOT) in enterprises and their management; - management of resources in enterprises, with a focus on labor resources; - a strategic approach to making management decisions in enterprises; - development and development of strategic management thinking.

The entrepreneur must possess a substantial quantity of knowledge and abilities to examine and implement all of these issues thoroughly. Consequently, strategic management is the formulation of a guiding philosophy for the implementation of a distinct visionary plan. In other words, the talent of distinct management necessitates that private enterprises and organizations be viewed as instruments for achieving domestic and international market objectives. In this respect, among sophisticated foreign nations, Japan's experience piques our interest the most.

In recent years, Japan has made significant advancements in enterprise strategic management and is now a global leader in this field. In management science, the "kanban" procedure is the most effective. Its essence is a management system that assures continuous production, the transformation of basic materials into finished goods, and the delivery of those goods to consumers. This management style consists of the following elements: Evaluation of the skills of selecting and hiring employees; training and professional development; setting explicit objectives and tasks for employees; changing positions; reorganization of the workforce. Certification is a defining feature of Japanese management. In addition, in accordance with the principle of training national management personnel of Japanese companies, they are accustomed to dispatching future managers graduating from management universities in the country to complete apprenticeships at the subsidiaries of the companies abroad. It is anticipated that the university-educated manager will return to the same organization. Personnel in Provardi who have accumulated the most experience over time are disseminated to the most essential managerial positions in the nation. In Japan, staff shortages have been eliminated due to this tradition.

The Japanese view management as requiring, first and foremost, diligence and a willingness to make personal sacrifices when necessary. The company's employees are raised in the spirit of a large family, and the company's interests are prioritized over all others. Even during meals, managers and employees are always present. Their fate is regarded as identical. The separation from the organization resembles mortality.

It can be concluded that the principles and methods of Japanese management can be applied to our circumstances, taking into account our national traditions and values. These are the building blocks for a new approach to business management in our nation. Consequently, the tasks of creating a strategy are the analysis of general industry tasks and competition, the analysis of the company's circumstances, and the study of theoretical and practical knowledge about the factors that determine the competitive strategy of the company.

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From the foregoing, it is evident that conducting strategic management necessitates strategic planning. Consequently, it is the responsibility of theorists to instill the philosophy of strategic planning in the minds of today's youthful entrepreneurs. Consequently, this cannot be achieved without taking risks and perils into consideration. Therefore, the modern entrepreneur must have a comprehensive understanding of what risk is and the material and moral harm it causes. This belief, however, makes the entrepreneur the center of attention every day. This issue also necessitates a rigorous scientific approach to its investigation. At its foundation, risk is the possibility of unfavorable outcomes, such as profit loss and other causes of damage. In Russian, it is known as a peril.

In other words, a risk is: - an action taken with the hope that the outcome will be positive, assuming the possibility of danger; - the risk of complete or partial loss of resources or income; - a natural state or situation for any courageous manager in the face of uncertainty; - to be more specific, it refers to the quantitative evaluation of a negative outcome. If viewed from a spiritual perspective, this issue is an entire philosophy of poor fate. Yes, fortune and misfortune form a dialectical unity. In order to avoid being exposed to it, merchants insure the property and even the behavior of private enterprises. As an exception, we must not neglect that some hazards cannot be covered by insurance. However, there is only one assurance for all of them, and that is the establishment of a reserve fund.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, formation of management thinking in new entrepreneurs, implementation of management strategy in small business and entrepreneurial enterprises is of great importance nowadays. The management strategy consists in aligning the capabilities of enterprises with the market situation, defining complex means of achieving the goals set to lift the population out of poverty. Therefore, in accordance with the "Strategy of Development" of the administration, the rational implementation of the chosen strategy for the development of our country on renewal and modernization plays an important role in joining our country to the ranks of advanced and developing countries in the world. This encourages our businessmen to take responsibility for their

management primarily at the microeconomic level, that is, to provide employment to the population, reduce poverty, and improve their material well-being by ensuring the stable pace of socio-economic development in our country.

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